

Conference Abstract

Saproxylic beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) on an old beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) in Madonie Mountains (Sicily, Italy)

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Abstract

Saproxylic insects associated with old trees are seriously threatened in Europe and their habitat is severely decreased. Usually, old trees harbour a very diverse fauna of beetles with many rare species and red-listed saproxylic insect species. These insects live in the dead wood outside the tree (in branches or parts of the trunk), inside the tree hollows, in the debris, and in fungal fruit bodies.

During 2019 we collected saproxylic beetles near Monte Carbonara (Madonie Mountains, Sicily, Italy) at 1800 meters above sea level. Particularly, we studied a very old still standing beech (*Fagus sylvatica* L.), t with numerous cavities and parts of the trunk fallen to the ground.

Samples were collected by visually looking for beetles, on the ground and under leaves near the old beech, in its cavities and sifting the debris in the laboratory.

Up to date the results include interesting beetle species such as *Osmoderma cristinae* Sparacio, 1994 (Cetoniidae), *Byrrhus numidicus* Normand, 1935 (Byrrhidae), *Rosalia alpina* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Morimus asper* Sulzer, 1776 (Cerambycidae).

Keywords

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